

Leveraging Large Language Models to Improve Healthcare Accessibility in Underdeveloped Countries

Healthcare is critical in underdeveloped countries. Due to the lack of a sufficient number of doctors, nurses, medical equipment, essential medicines, and trained support staff, many individuals are unable to access proper healthcare. For example, Nigeria, with a population of more than 215 million people, has an average of 3.8 doctors per 10,000 people. Many people even lose their lives to preventable causes. This work provides a framework for how Large Language Models (LLMs) can be leveraged to provide better health diagnoses and personalised health recommendations. Given the widespread use of mobile phones, even in underdeveloped countries, the system takes advantage of this tool for better recording of medical records, patient education and monitoring critical conditions. This study relies on a mobile application, Berry, to serve this purpose. The application was provided to 83 respondents, and a survey with critical questions was conducted afterwards. For most of the questions, an overwhelming 85% of the users responded with a score of 4 or 5, with 5 being the maximum score. The results indicate the potential for LLMs to shorten the gap in healthcare accessibility and assist patients in receiving healthcare irrespective of geographical and economic constraints.

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Introduction

In the last century, technological advancements and medical discoveries have brought about an increase in the quality of life for many individuals in various regions. However, this is not the case in many underdeveloped countries where there is a disparity in healthcare access. This disparity has worsened due to socioeconomic factors, limited resources that lead to a persistent healthcare crisis and underreporting of the actual situation. This challenge has resulted in a tremendous loss of lives. The issue becomes more severe as the number of medical professionals is insufficient. This results in the neglect of preventable diseases, which leads to very high mortality rates and a significant decrease in quality of life for many individuals. Furthermore, while there has been an increased effort by many organizations to address these problems, the progress remains limited due to factors such as sudden population growth, which leads to further strain on the already overwhelmed healthcare system. For example, the population of Nigeria, one of the most populous countries, has increased by more than 200% in the last 50 years. Additionally, the ratio of doctors to patients, which is about 4 doctors for 10,000 individuals, is alarmingly low in Nigeria. These figures illustrate a critical challenge concerning the healthcare system and highlight a need for technological solutions. The population increase, coupled with the under-resourced health facilities and the shortage of healthcare professionals, results in many individuals, especially in remote areas, having limited access to professional medical care. As a result, preventable diseases such as malaria and diarrhoea have claimed the lives of many individuals. Another factor that contributes to this crisis is the lack of proper education and healthcare awareness. For example, research by Omotoso et al. [1] suggests that cancer care inequality in some parts of Africa can be attributed to inadequate funding for research and poor cancer education. The authors propose solutions such as increasing awareness by the healthcare professions during hospital visits and encouraging screening, amongst other measures. Similarly, a work by Oleribe et al. [2] contains a survey to pinpoint the primary causes of healthcare challenges in Africa; 34.29% of the respondents suggest that the problem can be attributed to inadequate human resources, and 30% suggest that it is due to inadequate budgetary allocation for healthcare. The leading solution of the survey includes more capacity building for healthcare workers.

During the past several years, there has been a growing interest in leveraging machine learning (ML) in healthcare. This includes drug design, early detection of diseases, protein modelling, better medical image analyses, personalized treatment plans and using natural language processing for electronic health records. For example, in my work with Baday titled “Accelerating molecular Docking using machine learning”, we developed a framework to leverage a long short-term memory to accelerate the virtual screen stage of drug design. Our approach modelled molecular feature relationships using less than 1% of the dataset that traditional methods would use. This work is just one of other research endeavours attempting to address the challenge of drug design. In detecting diseases, a study by Sharma et al. [3] employed and compared different ML models, such as Random Forest, to predict cancer. They obtained very competitive results that can be used for the treatment of cancer. A work by Escudero et al. [4] provides a cost-effective method to detect Alzheimer’s, a very serious neurological disease that is often difficult to predict, especially in its early stages. Similarly, a work by Liu et al. [5] uses a deep neural network to diagnose Alzheimer’s disease and its prodromal stage, Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI). The authors indicated that the design workflow can require less labelled training data and can analyse multiple classes in one setting. Similarly, Wang et al. [6] utilized a deep neural network to detect

Parkinson's, another neurological disease that is difficult to detect accurately. The model was trained on a deep neural network on a small data set of 183 healthy individuals and 401 early Parkinson's disease patients. The resulting model exhibits an accuracy of 94.1% in detecting the disease.

Recently, there has been an increase in the computational capacities of computers. This advancement also enabled the improvements of learning algorithms for both vision and natural language processing. An example of this is Attention is all you need [13] from Google. The result is that large generative models trained on large datasets became possible. These models are also multimodal and can perform a variety of tasks. Examples of such models are GPT 4o [7], Gemina [8] and Llama[9] from Meta. There are also models, such as Veo [9], that can generate video outputs from text prompts. While the cost of the APIs of these models is high per token, the cost is gradually reducing due to the increase of the models in the market. For example, at the release of GPT 3 in 2022, the cost was \$0.06 per 1,000 tokens; however, today, it is around \$0.002 per 1,000 tokens for the powerful GPT -4o. This particular model can handle 128k of context. This indicates that it can grasp and analyse a huge chunk at a time. Ultimately, these advancements also mean that models can be leveraged to process medical records for robust personalised healthcare recommendations in underdeveloped countries. This can be proven by research from Eriksen et al., which showed that the recent most powerful GPT 4 can accurately diagnose 52.7% of complex medical case challenges, performing better than 99.98% of readers. This further underscores the potential of integrating large generative models to enhance diagnostic accuracy and patient care.

In this work, I aim to demonstrate how LLMs can be leveraged to provide more robust healthcare assistance to individuals in underdeveloped regions. I also aim to show that a smartphone, a tool widely used everywhere, can be harnessed to address the critical issue of healthcare in the region. I have developed Berry, a mobile app to facilitate healthcare access by improving the recording of medical records, providing personalised assistance and raising awareness. The application makes use of an LLM to provide context-specific assistance based on factors such as the user's dietary habits, medical conditions and data from smart connected devices such as a smartwatch. The ultimate goal of this endeavour is to democratise access to healthcare. In essence, these are the contributions of Berry. First, Berry provides diet and exercise suggestions based on user medical records, second, it provides the ability to chat with an LLM conditioned on user context, third, the app supports interaction in multiple local languages not known by many healthcare professionals, fourth Berry curates recommendations while considering regional factors, fifth, Berry utilizes data provided by other health monitoring apps like myfitnesspal to enrich the context, and lastly, Berry provides daily flashcards to education users.

Materials and Methods

Application's Component

The application is structured into three primary sections. The first section provides an interface for the user to input three distinct types of contexts: **Dietary Log, Health Records and Exercise Tools**. The **Dietary Log** subsection provides an interface for the user to log the meals the user consumes in a day. The interface also prompts the user to log the dishes within a meal. For example, the meal can be breakfast, and the dishes could be eggs, wheat bread, milk, tea and orange. The **Health Records** subsection is for medical records, it also provides an interface to document health issues. This includes logging the onset date of a condition and the medical department (for example, dentistry, cardiology and general). Additionally, users can input a detailed explanation of the condition and log in various medical test results associated with that health problem. The format of a test result can be pure text, PDF or an image file. Finally, the **Exercise Tools** subsection is for the users to input all the available exercise equipment at home and different exercises they enjoy. The overarching objective is to compile comprehensive data that will enrich the context provided to the LLM.

The app also features a separate tab to interact with the LLM based on the context mentioned in the previous sections. Moreover, a separate “Today” section provides users with suggestions for different meals and exercises for a particular day tailored to their context. The LLM chat is also conditioned with a prompt to avoid unrelated random questions and to improve the experience.

While the aforementioned sections can provide the basic data necessary for the generative model, most smartphones track data such as steps and walking distances that can provide a breadth of a user's health issues. Many smartwatches even capture critical data such as heart rate, respiratory rate, body temperature, blood oxygen and sleep data. This provides an opportunity to provide the LLM with an even more extensive and detailed context. This study makes use of GPT-4o with a context length of 128k tokens. A high context length enables the model to process a large amount of data in a single session.

The next section contains more detailed information on other data sources that are essential and useful. Figure 1 illustrates a flow diagram of the application.

Figure 1. Flow diagram of Berry

Data sources

This research utilizes health data collected from personal smartphones and connected accessories such as smartwatches and smart scales. The smartphone itself can track metrics such as steps and walking distance, flights claimed, active calories and more. Additionally, the connected devices can provide data that the phone’s hardware cannot capture. Table 1 shows the different data types and their sources.

Table 1. Data sources

Data type	Source
Heart Rate	Watch
Steps	Phone, Watch
Active Energy	Watch
Resting Energy	Watch
Walking + Running Distance	Phone, Watch
Stand Hours	Watch
Exercise Minutes	Watch
Sleep Analysis	Watch
Respiratory Rate	Watch
Oxygen Saturation (spO2)	Watch

Body Temperature	Watch
VO2 Max	Watch
ECG (Electrocardiogram)	Watch
Body Fat Percentage	Smart Scale
Muscle Mass	Smart Scale
Visceral Fat	Smart Scale
Basal Metabolic Rate (BMR)	Smart Scale

Machine Learning Models and Addressing Privacy

There are numerous powerful generative models available today. These include GPT-3 turbo, GPT-4o, and Llama 3. Some of these models provide APIs that are effective and relatively affordable, considering this pilot program. However, the downside of using such models is privacy. This is because user data shared with third parties faces the risk of data breach. Additionally, even though the APIs provide an option to opt out of using data for further training of LLMs, it is still critical due to the nature of the data, which is of a medical type. While the solution is to use open-source models for on-device inference, most smartphones lack the memory and computational capacity to run such large models. However, recent advancements in smartphones have integrated dedicated hardware to accelerate machine learning matrix processing that generative models rely on. The powerful GPT-4o was utilized in conducting this research due to the convenience of using an API. The application was designed to be used with different models, so in the future, the user can have the option to select among multiple models. Moreover, the only method of signing is exclusively through Apple or Google. This approach eliminates the overhead of managing a user's data and ultimately assists in protecting the data as these firms have strong privacy policies.

Results

Case Study and Pilot Program

To gather users' feedback, many individuals had to be recruited to test the app, this process spanned more than three 3 weeks. After that period, more than 90 individuals were identified. Out of that 90, 43 of the participants owned at least one smart connected device such as a smartwatch or a smart scale. These devices are important for collecting robust data to provide additional context to the LLM. The users were provided with the app for 2 months before the trial concluded. While this period might be enough, it still resulted in promising results.

At the end of that period, a survey with seven questions was provided to the app users. Out of the 90, only 83 responded. For privacy matters, I could not identify which users provided specific data from other apps. Such data include information on micronutrients for Vitamins like Vitamin A, C, D, E, and K and minerals like Calcium, Zinc, Iron, Sodium, Potassium, Phosphorus and Magnesium.

Additionally, when sending users' data to the API for processing, I opted not to use users' data for further training of the server models. While I am unaware of the nature of the data sent to the AP, the answers to the survey can still provide valuable insights about the app and its potential. Table 2 contains all the survey questions.

Table 2. Survey Questions

Question Number	Question	Possible answers
1	Your age group?	18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55+
2	How frequently did you use Berry?	Daily, Weekly
3	How likely are you to use the app again in the future	1-5
4	How likely are you to suggest Berry to a friend	1-5
5	Rate rate the accuracy, reliability, and relevance of the medical advice provided by model	1-5
6	Have you observed any improvement in your health since you started using Berry?	Yes/No
7	How satisfied are you with the diet recommendations provided by Berry?	1-5
8	How would you evaluate the Daily Exercise Recommendations?	1-5
9	To what extent has your awareness increased regarding any of your health conditions?	1-5

Demographics, Frequency, Likelihood to Continue, and Suggestions

Figure 2: Demographics, Frequency, Likelihood to Continue, and Suggestions

Figure 3: LLM Performance and User Satisfaction

LLM Performance and User Satisfaction

Survey Analyses

The result of the survey, after being presented to all the individuals, was generally positive. Figures 3, 4 and 5 can be observed to gain a virtual insight into the responses. Most of the app users were within the age range of 22-25 (36). There are also 30 users in the age range of 18-21. Additionally, there are 13 and 4 respondents in the age range of 26-29 and above the age of 30, respectively. In terms of Berry's usage, there was an overwhelming number (73) that used it daily and 10 respondents that used it weekly. Having a program with good engagement is crucial to making the survey robust. Also, this positive engagement indicates the app's relevance. In terms of ratings on the likelihood of continuing using the app after the program concludes, a majority of 74 respondents indicated a strong commitment, as 45 related this question as a 4 and 29 related it 5. Relating to this, I asked users about the likelihood of suggesting Berry to a friend. An overwhelming number of individuals (30) rated it as 5, and 30 rated it as 4. This further indicates that the users found the app useful and were willing to recommend it to others.

In addition, I wanted to gain insights into how users perceived the accuracy and relevance of the generated medical advice from the model. This result was also positive, as 53 of the users rated it very high, 30 ranked it as 5 and 23 ranked it as 4. Respondents were also prompted if they had observed any improvements regarding any underlying medical conditions. This was a particular question that received the lowest ranking as most (53) of the app users rated it as No. It could have been due to the short duration of the program, which is sufficient to notice any improvement in health. Such questions can be included in future surveys with a longer duration.

Furthermore, 63 out of the 83 participants rated the daily diet recommendations as either 4 or 5. This is also positive feedback as it is more than 75% of the users. Similarly, the daily exercise rating also received a positive response, as 68 of the respondents rated it high. As the final question, the users were also prompted to rate how their awareness has increased regarding any of their underlying medical conditions; an overwhelming number of the participants (74) rated it as either 4 or 5, indicating that the users found the feature beneficial. In General, with the exception of the 6th question, most of the results received a positive response.

Challenges and Limitations

One of the first challenges of this research was recruiting a broad range of individuals to join the program and to complete the survey. Users were also regularly followed up to ensure continued participation. This further increased the difficulty of having a robust sample size. This process was also time-consuming, as it spanned two months. The initial figure of the participants was more than 100, but due to significant attrition, only 90 of the individuals joined the final program. The participants were also offered gift cards as an incentive to join. Additionally, the significant challenge was recruiting individuals who actively use smart devices and an iPhone, as the app is only available on that platform. Moreover, the participants needed to be using the latest version of the iPhone operating system; this was one of the issues that narrowed the number of eligible users. Moreover, the need to increase diversity by including different genders from different backgrounds also presented another issue. My close proximity to a university partially alleviated this issue. However, the limitation of the study created a discrepancy between the demographic that the application targets (underdeveloped countries) and the actual participants. Due to the socio-economic factors in the target demography, the number of active smart devices such as smartphones was relatively low. However, while such devices can provide data that the

smartphone does not provide, the smartphone data can still be sufficient. Additionally, most of the app users were below the age of 30. Since most individuals above that age are more likely to need a Berry, not having older users might have affected the survey response. Additionally, the research would rely on continued funding to enhance Berry's capabilities to reach individuals from diverse backgrounds. While privacy is a critical issue due to the nature of the data shared through the API, I toggled on the API option that excludes the users' data from being used in further training of future generative models. Additionally, the limited statistics of the survey might not have shed light on the true potential of the usage of Berry. A more robust and diverse survey with individuals from different backgrounds would be required. This larger survey would also require better data analytics.

Future Work

Most health monitoring apps are affected by the issue of privacy, and Berry is not an exception. This is because, on many occasions, data has to be processed on an external server. A possible solution is to use open-source models that run on the device. As mobile phone hardware evolves, the possibility of running local models also increases. This is because more phones are equipped with hardware that is dedicated to accelerating complex matrix operations. Additionally, there are also lower parameter generative models that can make this transition even more feasible. Furthermore, since reliable internet access in underdeveloped countries is an issue, having a local model could completely mitigate both the issue of privacy and reliable internet. Furthermore, I intend to incorporate standalone models trained for specific tasks such as cancer and Alzheimer's [11] detection. Hugging Face, a platform that offers open-source models provides useful models that can be leveraged. I also intend to cooperate with non-governmental organisations (NGOs) to expand the application's access and impact. In essence, the positive perception of the app indicates its potential and serves as motivation to continue developing the app. There are also platforms like Apple's ResearchKit and Carekit [10] that can be explored to enable support for larger data collection to gain more insights into the potential of generative models for health monitoring. These particular frameworks can also increase the scope of the research to enable more tailored healthcare.

Conclusion

This research presents a novel methodology to address the critical challenge of healthcare in undeveloped countries with the use of large language models (LLMs). The application records and utilises users' diet available at home, medical records and exercise equipment at home as context to provide tailored recommendations for diet and exercise. It also features interaction with the model to ask questions and acquire information. Berry also leverages data from smartphone-connected gadgets such as smartwatches to increase the quality of the context. The mobile app was accompanied by a survey to gain insights into the potential of the app. After presenting 83 responses with 9 survey questions, the rating of the answers was overwhelmingly positive. Notably, more than 75% of the survey participants rated the exercise and diet recommendation by the LLM as either 4 or 5. More than 80% of the respondents rated the model's medical advice as relatively good. Even though the survey was limited in terms of respondents and diversity, the results indicate the prospect of leveraging large generative models for increased healthcare accessibility. The potential of using local models as smartphone hardware evolves is very encouraging. I also intend to work with more researchers and software developers to overcome some of the challenges of the app. In conclusion, the study highlights the potential of exploiting large language models to address the critical challenge of healthcare in underdeveloped countries.

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